

Synthesis of xanthenes from chromones[†]

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Abstract : Synthesis of xanthenes from chromones published till 2012 is reviewed.

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I. Introduction

The compounds containing xanthone (other names : 9-oxo-9H-xanthene, 9H-xanthen-9-one, dibenzo[b,e]-γ-pyrone) moiety **A** or its reduced form are abundant in nature. Naturally occurring as well as some synthetic xanthenes exhibit important biological activity. Consequently, search for efficient methods for synthesizing xanthenes bearing multiple and diverse substitution patterns is continued. The two significant synthetic routes to xanthenes basically involve ring closure on to either the oxygen atom of benzophenones or the carbonyl carbon atom of diphenyl ethers. Synthesis of xanthenes from benzynes and appropriate benzene derivatives also involves the non-isolable intermediates structurally akin to either benzophenone or diphenyl ether. The recent trend to construct xanthenes from the compounds containing chromone (other names : 4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 1-benzopyran-4-one, chromen-4-one, chromenone) moiety **B** has, however, attracted much attention. An overview of the synthesis of xanthenes mainly from benzophenones and diphenyl ethers was published in 2005¹. Progress report on the synthesis as well as chemistry of xanthenes, mingled with that of other six membered oxygen heterocycles, is scattered in several treatises in heterocyclic chemistry being published from time to time. So far only one exclusive, that too not so exhaustive, review on synthesis of xanthenes from chromones had appeared in 1999². Many publications have appeared since then and these warrant a cur-

rent review. The present article aims at giving a comprehensive account of the title topic covering literature available up to 2012; the works already incorporated in our previous review² are also briefly mentioned.

Synthesis of xanthone **A** from chromone **B** essentially involves the formation of ring C of the former in fusion with ring B of the latter. In most of such syntheses, C-2 and C-3 of **B** correspond to C-4a and C-9a, respectively of **A**. In the conversion of a chromone substrate having an either sp² or sp³ carbon linked to its 3-position to xanthone by a Michael initiated pyran ring opening and a subsequent pyran ring closure, it is the C-2 and the aforementioned carbon of the former constituting respectively C-9a and C-4a of the latter (*vide infra*). This review is presented in the following sections and subsections based on the class of carbon components, nature of the carbon framework of the chromone substrates and the types of reactions involved in the annulation processes. The reactions described here for chromones mostly having no substituent in their benzene A ring rarely affect alkyl, alkoxy, halogeno substituents, if present, in that benzene ring.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.
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II. Annulation of four-carbon components with the 2,3-olefinic bond of chromone

II.1. [4+2]Cyclisation involving Michael initiated ring closure (MIRC) reactions

The chromone **1** because of its enone moiety can function as a good Michael acceptor. So a Michael donor having also an electrophilic carbon centre is likely to undergo MIRC reaction with chromone. This methodology has been adopted to annulate chromone **1** with an appropriate four-carbon component leading to tetrahydroxanthone or xanthone. Thus, an enolisable α,β -unsaturated ketone undergoes MIRC with chromone **1** in the presence of *t*-butyldimethylsilyl triflate and 2,6-lutidine to form a tetrahydroxanthone (a *cis*-adduct) that can be dehydrogenated by DDQ³. Similar base-catalysed MIRC reaction between 1-(phenylsulfonyl)isobenzofuran-3-one and chromone with concomitant elimination of phenylsulfonic acid leads to a dihydroxybenzo[*b*]xanthone. This methodology has been adopted for the preparation of bikaverin **9**, a naturally occurring antiprotozoal agent. Condensation of chromone **6** with isobenzofuranone **7** in the presence of lithium *t*-butoxide gives benzo[*b*]xanthone **8** which on sequential oxidation with silver carbonate – celite (Fetizon reagent) and demethylation by LiI in DMF affords bikaverin **9**⁴.

- 1: X = H
 2: X = CHO
 3: X = CO₂H
 4: X = CO₂R
 5: X = S(O)C₆H₄Cl-*p*

6

7

8

9

A cascade reaction sequence of [4+2]annulation of the zwitterion **11**, generated by addition of tri-*n*-butylphosphine to the allene **10**, with 3-formylchromone **2**, followed by deformylation affords the tetrahydroxanthone **12** that can be dehydrogenated by DDQ under microwave heating in 1,2-dichlorobenzene to the xanthone **13**⁵.

10: R = H, Ph, CO₂Et

11

12

13

The zwitterion **14** (E = CO₂Me or CO₂Et, X = Me or NMe₂) arising from acetylene dicarboxylate and the catalyst 4-picoline or 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) gets annulated with the 2,3-olefinic bond of 3-formylchromone having an electron-withdrawing bromo or nitro group at its 6-position and the resultant annulated intermediate ultimately gives the xanthone **15** (R = Br or NO₂) by an organocatalysed elimination process. In contrast, the organocatalysed reaction of 3-formylchromone **2** and its 6-chloro- and 6-methyl-analogues leads to benzophenones **16** if catalysed by DMAP or to pyrano[4,3-*c*]chromones **17** if catalysed by 4-picoline⁶.

14

15

16

17

For **16-17**: R = H, Cl, Me

II.2. [4+2]Cycloaddition

Chromone **1** can function as a dienophile only towards a diene with *o*-quinodimethane structure (*vide infra*). The presence of an electron-withdrawing group at its 3-position enhances its dienophilicity. Thus, 3-substituted chromones **2-5** undergo Diels-Alder (D-A) reaction with various dienes, the stability of the cycloadduct depending on the nature of X group^{7,8}. The cycloadduct derived from **5** and Danishefsky's diene is prone to undergo aromatization to 3-hydroxyxanthone via *syn*-elimination of *p*-chlorobenzenesulfenic acid and 1,4-elimination of methanol⁷.

D-A reaction of 3-formylchromone **2** with *o*-benzoquinodimethane **19**, generated *in situ* by thermal decomposition of benzothiophene-2,2-dioxide **18** (R = H, Br; R¹ = H, OMe), gives a stereoisomeric mixture of the adducts **20** which on refluxing with DMSO-I₂ is dehydrogenated to xanthone **21** admixed with a small amount of naphthyl phenyl ketone **22**⁹. [4+2]Cycloaddition of indole-*o*-quinodimethane **23**, generated by treating 1-benzoyl-2,3-bis(bromomethyl)indole with sodium iodide in DMF or PhMe containing 18-crown-6 under reflux, with chromone **1** is neither regioselective nor stereoselective in giving a diastereoisomeric mixture of the adducts **24** and **25**. Cycloadducts of **23** with 3-formylchromone **2** also give the same mixture of **24** and **25** after *in situ* deformylation^{10,11}. D-A reaction of 3-formylchromone with pyrazole-*o*-quinodimethane **26** is regioselective giving only the stereoisomeric mixture of the cycloadduct **27**. On air oxidation, the adducts **24** and **25** are aromatized to the corresponding chromenocarbazoles and **27** to chromeno[3,2-*f*]indazole¹¹.

III. [3+3]Annulation

Construction of xanthone framework **A** by annulation of a three-carbon component with the chromone framework **C** as well as **D** is feasible. Base-catalysed condensation of active methylene compounds with 3-acyl-2-thiomethylchromone gives xanthenes by a Michael addition - thiomethanol elimination - cyclisation sequence. As for example, **28** (R¹ = H, Me, Ph) in the presence of potassium *t*-butoxide gives **29** (R² = H, R³ = Ac) with acetylacetone and **29** (R² = R³ = CO₂Et) with diethyl β -ketoglutarate¹².

Sodium naphthalenide-induced conversion of 3-methoxycarbonylchromone **4** (R = Me) into 4-hydroxy-3-salicyloylxanthone **33** is an example of a [3+3]annulation, the three-carbon component being provided by the chromone ester **4** itself. The said conversion has been rationalized by an intramolecular acyloin-type condensation of the initially formed dimer **30** (\rightarrow **31**), pyran ring openings (\rightarrow **32**) and recyclisation (Scheme 1)¹³.

Scheme 1. Sodium naphthalenide-induced conversion of 3-methoxycarbonylchromone into 4-hydroxy-3-salicyloylxanthone.

The formation of xanthone **A** in 11% yield by subjecting 3-bromo-2-methylchromone **34** to Heck reaction with acrolein dimethyl acetal **35**, followed by aqueous work-up of the reaction mixture has been rationalized in the following way. Hydrolysis of the initially formed 3-vinylchromone **36** forms β -(2-methyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-3-yl)acrolein that either by intramolecular aldol condensation or by 1,6-electrocyclisation of the enol **37** through its *cisoid* conformer **37'** (R = H), followed by water elimination gives xanthone (Scheme 2)¹⁴. The present author anticipates that xanthone **A** arises even before aqueous work-up of the reaction mixture. The initially formed Heck product **36** affords the triene **37** (R = Me) by base-catalysed 1,6-elimination of MeOH, its conformer **37'** (R = Me) giving xanthone by electrocycloisatation and subsequent methanol elimination.

IV. Annulation of two-carbon components

Synthesis of xanthenes can be conceptualized by annulation of two-carbon components with the chromone derivatives having the general carbon frame-works as in

Scheme 2. Formation of xanthone by Heck reaction of 3-bromo-2-methylchromone with acrolein dimethyl acetal.

E, F and G. A few compounds of the type **E** participate through the corresponding *o*-quinodimethane structure **E'** in some D-A reactions. Chromones having carbon skeleton **G** are often converted to non-isolable intermediates of carbon frame-work **E**. 2-Vinylchromones are the representative members of the general carbon frame-work **F** while 3-alkenyl- and 3-alkynylchromones are those of **G**.

IV.1. Annulation with the chromone system **E**

The benzopyranonphthalide **39**, a representative member of the system **E**, undergoes lithium *t*-butoxide-catalysed MIRC with an α,β -unsaturated ketone or ester $R^1CH=$

CHCOR² to give 1,4-dihydroxyxanthone **40**. Methyl crotonate, cyclohexenone, coumarin and 1,2-dihydro-1,1-dimethoxynaphthalen-2-one have been used as Michael acceptors in this annulation process¹⁵.

When the pyrano-fused cyclobutenedione **41**, derived from dithiane-protected salicylaldehyde and dialkylsquaric acid, is treated with the alkenyl lithiate **42** (R¹, R² = H, alkyl) and the reaction quenched with acetic anhydride, the xanthone **44** results. This annulation is initiated by the nucleophilic addition of the lithiated derivative at the carbonyl away from the bulky dithiane moiety. Similar regioselective condensation of the hetaryl lithiate **43** (X = O, S, NH; R¹, R² = H, alkyl) with **41** produces **46**. HgCl₂ can convert **44** and **46** to the xanthenes **45** and **47**, respectively¹⁶.

The hydrazone **48**, derived from 3-acetylchromone and 1,1-dimethylhydrazine, on being refluxed with *N*-phenylmaleimide (NPM) in toluene gives mainly the tetrahydroxanthone **51** with a little amount of 3-cyano-2-methylchromone, the former arising through normal D-A reaction of the enehydrazine tautomer **50** (R = NMe₂) of **48** with NPM and the latter by elimination of

dimethylamine. The anil **49**, like the hydrazone **48**, undergoes D-A reaction through **50** (R = C₆H₄Me-*p*) with NPM to give the tetrahydroxanthone **52**. Palladised charcoal converts **51** to xanthone **53** by dehydrazination and dehydrogenation, and **52** to **54** by dehydrogenation¹⁷.

Deacylative dimerisation of 3-acetylchromone **55** on treatment with NaOEt in EtOH to xanthone **61** first reported by Menichi *et al.*¹⁸ has been rationalized in the following way¹⁹. Under base catalysis 3-acetylchromone **55** undergoes an acyl-acyl rearrangement to 3-formyl-2-methylchromone **56**; its tautomer **58** having an *o*-quinodimethane structure gives with the substrate **55** the normal D-A adduct **60** (X = Ac, Y = O) that is ultimately aromatised to xanthone **61**.

3-Formyl-2-methylchromone **56** as well as its hydrazone **57** (≡ **48**) can form **61** with any of the chromones (1-3, **55**) even without any added base through the intermediacy of the corresponding D-A adduct **60**. It should be particularly mentioned here that 2,3-unsubstituted chromone can function as a dienophile towards *o*-quinodimethane as **58** and **59**¹⁹. Conversion of 3-formyl-2-methylchromone **56** in contact with Brockman 'neutral' alumina into xanthone **61** involves isomerisation of the former to 3-acetylchromone **55**, followed by their condensation²⁰. The xanthone **62** results from the pyridine-piperidine-catalysed self-condensation of chromone **56** whereas pulverized sodium brings about self-condensation of 3-acetylchromone **55** to xanthone **63**²¹. Phenyldiazomethane brings about to some extent

benzylation of 3-formylchromone **2** at its 2-position; 2-benzyl-3-formylchromone thus formed condenses with the substrate **2** and the resultant condensate ultimately gives 4-phenyl-2-salicyloylxanthone by a sequence of water elimination, deformylation and pyran ring opening. Both the condensation process and transformation of the condensate to the aforementioned xanthone are base catalysed, phenyldiazomethane or the 1-pyrazoline derived from **2** and phenyldiazomethane functioning as the base catalyst²².

55

56: Y = O
57: Y = NNMe₂58: Y = O
59: Y = NNMe₂

60

61: R¹ = R² = H
62: R¹ = H, R² = Me
63: R¹ = R² = Me

IV.2. Annulation with chromone system F

The wrong structure **65** previously assigned without any spectroscopic data²³ to the cycloadduct obtained from *E*-2-styrylchromone **64** (R¹ = H, R² = Ph) and maleic anhydride or NPM has been rectified as the 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone **66** (R¹ = H, X = O or NPh)²⁴. The cycloaddition of *E*-2-(1-methylstyryl)chromone **64** (R¹ = Me, R² = Ph) with the aforesaid dienophiles gives a stereoisomeric mixture **66** (R¹ = Me, X = O, NPh)²⁴. Here the D-A (*endo*-addition) reactions are clearly followed by 1,3-hydrogen shift from C-9a to C-4 so as to form the resonance stabilized chromone system. In the light of this result, the reported structures of the cycloadducts of maleic anhydride or NPM²⁵, dibenzoyl ethenes²⁶ and 1,4-benzoquinones²⁷ with 2-styrylchromones may also need revision. Tetrahydroxanthone **66** can be easily aromatized.

[4+2]Cycloaddition between 2-vinylchromone **64** (R¹ = H, R² = Ph, 2-methoxy-phenyl, 2,4-dichlorophenyl, 2-thienyl, 2-furfuryl, Me) and the pyrrolidine enamine **67** with concomitant 1,3-hydrogen shift and elimination of pyrrolidine gives the dihydroxanthone **68**, sometimes along with a small quantity of 1-methylidene isomer **69**, that readily gives xanthone **70** by air oxidation. The compound **69** in contact with AcOH-H₂SO₄ for a few hours is also converted into **70**²⁸. The enamine, derived from pyrrolidine and acetaldehyde, reacts with **64** (R¹ = H, R² = Ph) to give the 1-unsubstituted xanthone **71**. A similar reaction between the enamine, obtained from pyrrolidine and propanal, with **64** (R¹ = H, R² = 2-thienyl) yields **72**²⁸. The reaction between 2-vinylchromone **64** (R¹ = Me, Ph; R² = Ph; R¹ = H; R² = Me, 2-furyl) and 1-pyrrolidinylcyclopentene **73** gives the xanthone derivative **74** analogous to **69**⁷

64

65

66

67

68

69

70

71: R² = Ph, R³ = Me
72: R² = 2-thienyl, R³ = Et

73

74

Several alkynes and alkenes function as two-carbon components to annulate with *E*-2-(2-dimethylaminovinyl)-chromone **75**. The cyclobutene **77**, initially formed by [2+2]cycloaddition of dienamine **75** with electrophilic acetylene **76**, undergoes further transformation depending on the nature of the X-group^{29,30}. Thus, the adducts **77** from **75a** with DMAD (**76a**), dibenzoylacetylene (**76b**) and ethyl propiolate (EP, **76c**), respectively give by a sequence of electrocyclic ring opening (\rightarrow **78**), electrocycloisatation and dimethylamine elimination the xanthenes **79a-c**, the last one being admixed with the flavone **80a** (Scheme 3). The enamine **75b** gives **79a** and **79d** with DMAD, and **79c** and **80b** with EP. Reaction of **75c** with DMAD affords **79e** exclusively.

Scheme 3. Reaction of *E*-2-(2-dimethylaminovinyl)chromone **75** with alkyne **76**.

The [4+2]cycloadduct **81** (non-isolable) initially obtained by reacting dienamine **75a** with NPM in DMF under reflux gives the xanthone **82** by spontaneous elimination of dimethylamine and dehydrogenation, NPM be-

ing the dehydrogenating agent^{29,30}. [4+2]Cycloaddition between **75a** and the chromones **2** and **3** is also known; **75a** in refluxing DMF gives the xanthone **83a** exclusively with the acid **3** but a mixture of **83a-b** with the aldehyde **2**³⁰.

Treatment of the enaminone **75a** with acetic anhydride-pyridine furnishes a mixture of the xanthenes **87** and **88**². The formation of both these products proceeds through initial β -acetylation of the enamine **75a** to **84**, the latter functioning as a dienophile as well as an electron-deficient diene to undergo [4+2]cycloaddition with the former. Thus, the cycloadduct **85** arising from the normal D-A reaction between the dienamine **75a** with the denophilic Me₂N-CH=C-Ac moiety of **84** (Scheme 4 - path *a*) undergoes base-catalysed deamination and deacylative deamination to give **87**. The umpolung D-A (inverse electron-demand D-A) reaction between electron-deficient diene **84** with the electron-rich enamine moiety of **75a** forms the cycloadduct **86** that affords **88** by elimination of two molecules of dimethylamine (Scheme 4 - path *b*).

3-Iodoflavone when subjected to Heck reaction with an excess (~2 equivalent) of diphenylacetylene **90a** produces a mixture of the benzo[*c*]xanthone **91a** and tetrasubstituted furan **92a**. This annulation process is regioselective as evident from the formation of **91b** and **92b** in similar Heck reaction between **89** and unsymmetrically substituted acetylene **90b**³¹.

For **85** and **86**
 $\text{Y} = 4\text{-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-2-yl}$

Scheme 4. Formation of xanthenes by acetylation of *E*-2-(2-dimethylaminovinyl)chromone.

For **90-92**
a: $\text{R}^1 = \text{R}^2 = \text{Ph}$
b: $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}, \text{R}^2 = \text{CMe}_3$

IV.3. Annulation of two-carbon components to chromone system G

IV.3.1. [4+2]Cycloaddition of 3-(2-substituted vinyl)chromones

IV.3.1.1. Normal D-A reaction

D-A Reaction of 3-styrylchromone **93** (Ar = phenyl, *m*-chloro- and *m*-methoxyphenyl) with *N*-methyl- and *N*-phenylmaleimide has been accomplished under microwave irradiation. D-A reactions of both *Z*- and *E*-isomers of the aforesaid 3-styrylchromone with *N*-methylmaleimide gives the cycloadducts in a stereoselective manner, *Z*-isomer giving the *endo*-adduct **94** (R = Me) and *E*-isomer, the *exo*-adduct **95** (R = Me). Predominant formation of the *exo*-adduct **95** (R = Ph) from the *Z*-isomer of **93** and less reactive NPM involves conversion of *Z*-isomer to *E*-isomer, followed by D-A reaction³². Some of the cycloadducts (**94** and **95**) undergo *in situ* oxidation whereas others require oxidation by DDQ so as to form the fully aromatized 4-aryl-1,3-dioxopyrrolo[3,4-*c*]xanthenone³³. The cycloadduct **97**, derived from *Z*-3-styrylchromone **93** and 2-(2-nitrovinyl)thiophene, spontaneously eliminates HNO_2 giving the xanthenone **98**³³. D-A reactions of several 3-(2-hetarylvinyl)chromones with maleic anhydride are also known³⁴.

The 3,4-dihydroxanthones **99** ($R^1, R^2, R^3 = H, Me$) having their diene portion locked in the *cisoid*-configuration undergo facile D-A reaction with various dienophiles³⁵. DMAD reacts with **99** ($R^1-R^3 = H$) and ($R^1 = H; R^2 = R^3 = Me$) in boiling bromobenzene to give the same xanthene dicarboxylic ester **101** as a result of an initial [4+2]cycloaddition (\rightarrow **100**) and a subsequent retro-Diels-Alder elimination of the alkyl bridge in the form of ethene and isobutene, respectively³⁵.

For **100-101**: $E = CO_2Me$

Intermolecular [4+2]cycloaddition involving the diene system present in 3-(2-acetylvinylchromone) **102** with the acetyl olefinic functionality (dienophile) of its second molecule has been utilized for the synthesis of naturally occurring vinaxanthone. When a solution of **102** in PhMe with 4.0 equivalent of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methoxyphenol (DTBMP) is heated in a sealed tube at 200 °C for 24 h with air, the cycloadduct **103** (non-isolable) gives xanthone **105** (40%) by aromatization and benzophenone **104** (5%) by pyran ring opening. The intermolecular cycloaddition is not regioselective, the regioisomer **107** producing the deacylated products **108** and **109** in respectively 17% and 5% yields. The additive DTBMP is assumed to be oxidized to quinone that brings about aromatization of **103** to **105** and of **107** to **108**. Demethylation of dimethoxyxanthone **105** by $AlCl_3$ in PhMe at 110 °C gives vinaxanthone **106**³⁶.

IV.3.1.2. IEDDA reaction

IEDDA reaction of vinylchromone **110** ($EWG = COMe, COPh, CO_2Et, CONEt_2, SO_2Ph, CN, Ar$) with

Scheme 5. Intermolecular [4+2]cycloaddition of 3-(2-acetylvinyl)chromone **102**.

electron-rich ethene **111** ($R = R^1 = OMe; R = H, R^1 = NMe_2$) is followed by elimination to produce the xanthone **112**³⁷. 5-Hydroxychromone **113** with ethyl vinyl ether produces xanthone **114** along with two other products³⁸. It is relevant to mention here that the reaction between **110** ($EWG = CO_2Et$) and several acyclic or cyclic enamine **115** ($X = H, Y = Ph; X = Ph, Y = H; XY = CH_2(CH_2)_{1-4}CH_2$) involves a domino IEDDA, elimination of dialkylamine and pyran ring opening to give benzophenone **116**, no xanthone being formed at all³⁹.

(Scheme 7). In this condensation, the 2,3-olefinic carbons of **117** function as the two-carbon component.

Scheme 6. Xanthenes from 3-alkynylchromones and active methylene compounds.

IV.3.2. Annulation with 3-alkynylchromones

A Chinese group has a major contribution in the synthesis of xanthenes by annulation of two-carbon components with 3-alkynylchromones⁴⁰⁻⁴³. An active methylene compound as **118** ($R^2 = \text{Me}, n\text{-Pr}, n\text{-Bu}, \text{Ph}$) reacts with 3-alkynylchromone **117** ($R^1 = \text{Ph}, p\text{-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4, p\text{-F}_3\text{CC}_6\text{H}_4, n\text{-pentyl}, \text{SiMe}_3$) in the presence of DBU to give the trisubstituted xanthone **120** through a domino process of Michael addition – pyran ring opening (\rightarrow **119**) and double cyclisation (Scheme 6). Dimethyl malonate similarly reacts with **117** giving **120** ($R^2 = \text{OH}$)⁴⁰. The chromone **117** with the active acetonitrile $R^2\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ ($R^2 = \text{CN}, \text{CONH}_2, \text{Ph}, \text{Ar}$) in DMF under DBU catalysis and microwave irradiation gives the xanthone **121**⁴¹.

3-Alkynylchromone **117** when heated in DMF containing DBU as the base catalyst self-condenses to 2-(1-alkynyl)xanthone **124** admixed in a very few cases with 2-salicyloylxanthone **125**⁴². Here self-condensation of **117** leads to the condensate **123** via **122**; a retro-Diels-Alder of **123** affords **124**, and **123** is aromatized to **125** by base (or water-)catalysed dealkynative pyran ring opening

3-Alkynyl-2-methylchromone **126** condenses with its lower homologue **117** (R^1 as before) and itself in DMSO under DBU catalysis and microwave irradiation to give the xanthenes **129** and **130**, respectively⁴³. This condensation involves a domino process of Michael initiated ring opening (\rightarrow **127**), ring closure, followed by a second ring opening (\rightarrow **128**) and ring closure (Scheme 8). This reaction mechanism reveals that C-2 along with C-2-bonded methyl carbon of **126** functions as a two-carbon component to get annulated with $>\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}\equiv\text{C}-\text{R}^1$ moiety of the chromone **117** or **126**.

3-Iodochromone **131** in its Heck reaction with the alkyne **132** initially forms the 3-alkynylchromone **133** (isolable) that affords by a [4+2]benzannulation the disubstituted xanthone **134**⁴⁴.

V. [5+1]Cyclisation

When subjected to Vielsmeier-Haak reaction (DMF- POCl_3), 3-acetyl-2-methylchromone and 3-acetyl-2-(2-dimethylaminovinyl)chromone **75b** give 1-chloroxanthenes **135** and **136**, respectively²¹.

Scheme 7. Self-condensation of 3-alkynylchromone 117.

Scheme 8. Base catalysed condensation of 3-alkynyl-2-methylchromone with itself or its lower homologue.

VI. [6+0]Cyclisation

VI.1. Chemical method

On heating under reflux in DMF, the dienamine **75b** cyclises through electrocycloislation of its enol tautomer, followed by elimination of dimethylamine to afford 1-hydroxyxanthone **137**. The enaminone **75b** in refluxing NaOMe-MeOH also gives the same xanthone **137**. The yields of **137** in both these processes are in the range of 37–47%. A chloroform solution of **75b** on treatment with excess bromine gives the dibromoxanthone **138** which is also obtained by bromination of **137**³⁰. The diarylchromone **139** (R¹ = H; R² = OMe; R¹ = R² = OMe) on diazotization followed by heating with copper powder (Ppschorr cyclisation) gives dibenzo[*a,c*]xanthone **140**^{45,46}. *E,E*-2-

135: $R^1 = \text{CHO}, R^2 = \text{H}$

136: $R^1 = \text{H}, R^2 = \text{CHO}$

(4-Arylbutadien-1-yl)chromone **141** ($R = \text{H}, \text{Me}, \text{OMe}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_2$) when heated under reflux in TCB containing iodine undergoes electrocyclisation and subsequent oxidation to give ultimately 1-arylxanthone **142**⁴⁷. The cycloadduct of 3-formylchromone and ethyl vinyl ether on treatment with acetone under acidic conditions gives the diketone **143**; the corresponding oxime **144** on heating under reflux in nitrobenzene undergoes electrocyclisation and subsequent oxidation to the oxime **145** of 4-acetylxanthone⁴⁸.

137: $X = \text{H}$

138: $X = \text{Br}$

139

140

141

146

147

142

143: $Z = \text{O}$

144: $Z = \text{NOH}$

148

149

145

150

[6+0]Cyclisation of several 2,3-distyrylchromones to 2,3-diarylxanthenes is known⁴⁹⁻⁵¹. *E,E*-2,3-Distyrylchromone **146** ($R^1, R^2 = \text{H}, \text{OMe}; R^3 = R^4 = \text{H}$), prepared from 3-bromo-2-methylchromone by Heck reaction with the appropriate styrene, followed by aldol condensation with benzaldehyde, on refluxing in TCB gives the diarylxanthone **147** together with minor amounts of 2,3-diaryl-3,4-dihydroxanthone **148** and the corresponding 1,2-dihydroisomer, the latter two converting into the former by prolonged refluxing in TCB. When 3-bromo-2-styrylchromone **149** ($R^3, R^4 = \text{H}, \text{OMe}$) is subjected to Heck reaction with 4,3- $R^1R^2C_6H_3-CH=CH_2$ ($R^1, R^2 = \text{H}, \text{OMe}$) in the presence of $\text{Pd}(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_4$ catalyst, the resultant distyrylchromone gives xanthone **147** by electrocyclisation and oxidation process under the reaction conditions (NMP, PPh_3 , Et_3N , 160° to reflux), a little amount of **148** being also isolated. The xanthenes **147** having one or two hydroxy substituents in either or both of the 2,3-diaryl moieties have been synthesized by the above referred methods and tested for their ROS-(reactive oxygen species) and RNS-(reactive nitrogen species) scavenging properties. The xanthone **147** ($R^1-R^4 = \text{OH}$) is found to be a promising candidate for scavenging superoxide radical⁵².

Base-catalysed condensation between 3-vinylchromone **110** (EWG = COMe, COAr) and 3-acetyl-2-methylchromone involves a cascade of several bond-breaking and bond-making processes and the ultimate intermediate undergoes *in situ* [6+0]cyclisation to the xanthone **150** (R = Me, Ar)⁵³.

Trifluoromethanesulfonic acid converts the lactone **151**, obtainable from 3-methoxycarbonyl-2-methylchromone and cyclohexanone, into cyclohexano[*b*]xanthone **152**⁵⁴. The chromone derivative **153**, obtainable from 3,5-dihydroxytoluene, β -(2,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)propionitrile and diethyl oxalate, has been converted in six steps into bikaverin **9**⁵⁵. The diketobenzopyran ester **154** has been cyclised to the xanthone ester **155**⁵⁶. It will not be out of context to mention here the formation of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone by treating 2-spiro(cyclopentane)-chromanone **156** with thallium(III) nitrate in the absence or presence of an acid catalyst like boron trifluoride etherate, *p*-toluenesulfonic acid or perchloric acid^{57,58}. Treatment of **156** with hydroxyl(tosyloxy)iodobenzene in MeCN under heat or ultra sound⁵⁹ also leads to tetrahydroxanthone that can be dehydrogenated by DDQ in dioxane under reflux⁵⁸.

VI.2. Photochemical method

3-(2-Methylbenzoyl)chromone in benzene on UV-irradiation gives the benzo[*b*]xanthone **157** by a sequence of photoenolisation, cyclisation and air oxidation⁶⁰. Irradiation of methanolic solutions of 2,3-diarylchromones in the presence of iodine gives dibenzo[*a,c*]xanthenes. For example, 2,3-diphenylchromone gives the xanthone **140** (R¹ = R² = H)⁴⁶. Several *E*-2-styrylchromones have been converted to benzo[*a*]xanthenes by photo-oxidative electrocyclic cyclisation^{61,62}. For example, chromone **158** (R¹ = R³ = H; R² = Ph) and *E*-2-styrylisoflavone **158** (R¹ = H; R² = Ar; R³ = Ph) in benzene on UV-irradiation in the presence of iodine give respectively the unsubstituted benzo[*a*]xanthone **159** (R = R¹ = H)⁶¹ and the corresponding 5-aryl analogue **159** (R¹ = H, R = Ar)⁶². This reaction evidently proceeds through an *E*- to *Z*-photoisomerisation, followed by an electrocyclic photo-oxidative ring closure. The chromone **158** (R¹ = Me; R² = Ph; R³ = OH) in MeOH on UV-irradiation gives the xanthone **159** (R = H; R¹ = Me) together with the *Z*-isomer of the substrate and the furochromone **160**⁶³. Similar photocyclisation of **158** (R¹ = Me; R² = Ph; R³ = OCH₂Ph) in MeOH produces xanthone **159** (R¹ = Me; R = H) in poor yield along with three other products⁶⁴. Exposure of **158** (R¹ = H, Me, Et; R² = Ph, R³ = H) dissolved in CHCl₃ to daylight for 30–50 days results in the formation of benzoxanthone **159** (R = H)⁶⁵. Irradiation of 2-(2-pyridylvinyl)chromone **161** (anyone of X, X¹ and X² is N and the other two are CH) gives the fused heterocycle **162**⁶⁶. Photochemical oxidation of isoflavone **163** in MeOH containing iodine in the presence of air affords the benzo[*a*]xanthone **164** together with 2-formylthiophene and 2-formyl-7-methoxyisoflavone, the latter two heterocycles arising due to photo-oxidative cleavage of the exocyclic olefinic bond of the substrate⁶⁷.

Several *E*-3-styrylflavones have been converted to benzo[*c*]xanthenes. Thus, **165** (R¹-R⁴ = H, Me, OMe, Cl) in TCB containing iodine on UV-irradiation undergoes electrocyclic cyclisation and *in situ* oxidation to give 2-

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161 (X/X¹/X² = N; rest two : X/X¹/X² = CH)

162 (X, X¹, X² : as in 161) 163

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arylbenzo[c]xanthone **166** in 40–70% yield. On similar treatment flavone **165** (R¹ = NO₂; R²-R⁴ = H) produces a mixture of **166** (30%) and 6-hydroxybenzo[c]xanthone **167** (54%)⁶⁸.

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